

Disparities in Climate Change Policy in the United States: An Environmental Justice Perspective

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Abstract

Given the increasing amount of evidence suggesting a connection between climate change and health disparities, this study utilized a statistical approach to explore the relationship between climate policies in the United States, past temperature changes, and vulnerable populations. Little was previously known about disparities in policy adoption and underlying motivations at the state level. By analyzing data from the United States excluding D.C., Hawaii, and Puerto Rico, we assessed the relationship between minority demographics, temperature changes (2011-2021), and climate policies (2021). We found no direct link between policy adoption and prior temperature experiences or minority percentages. However, states with climate policies in place had consistently higher Asian American populations than those without such policies. Additionally, we found significant differences in the demographic composition of Black or African American populations in states with electricity policies in place compared to states without such policies. Lastly, we found that states with higher percentages of people below the poverty line were less likely to have carbon pricing and electricity sector portfolios plans in place. This suggests a nuanced relationship between policy types and demographic compositions within states, indicating a potential avenue for further exploration in understanding climate policy dynamics.

Key Words: Environmental justice, Climate Change, Public Policy

1. Introduction

In recent years growing media attention has focused on unusual shifts in temperature and weather patterns (Krajick, 2021; Phillips et al., 2022 Nations, 2022). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) records global temperatures 1.09 °C higher in the decade before 2020 than in the fifty years before 1900. It projects the potential for an increase in global temperature between 1 and 5.7 °C (1.8–10.3 °F) by 2100, with the 2015 COP Paris Agreement goal to limit the temperature increase to 1.5 C above pre-industrial levels (Arias et al., 2021). In the sixty years between the mid-1950s and 2010, a significant proportion of this increase is linked to human activity. Clear evidence relates changes in the climate system to the release of pollutants including methane, carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide. Use of fossil fuels for transportation, electricity, residential and commercial uses, agriculture, and manufacturing have been identified as causes (Turrentine, 2022; EPA, 2022).

In the United States, national studies recognize increases in temperature of 1.2°F (0.7°C) in the twenty-year period before 2016 compared to the fifty years before 1960 (Vose, 2017). National studies also identify unique challenges of extreme weather events, including heat waves and droughts (Marx, 2021; NCA 2014). Trenberth et al. (2007) found that almost three-quarters of land regions experienced a statistically significant increase (reduction) in warm (cold) nights. Changes in the arctic and jet stream cause temperature variability in the United States (Thomas &

Rapporteur, 2014). Extreme weather events and climate change have increasingly wide-ranging effects, including disrupting agricultural yields, and water supply, with subsequent impacts on insurance rates, public health, and other societal functions. Notable impacts in urban areas include heat islands (Zhou & Shepherd, 2010). Coumou and Rahmsdorf (2012) focus on climate threats and increased warming in the decade before 2011, as well as the increasing number and variety of extreme weather events in that year. They highlight studies showing rising rates of hot days in the United States and possible correlations between increases in average temperature, heat records, and drought.

Impacts from the weather are far-reaching in the United States, including posing threats to national security and GDP (Lazo et al., 2011; NAS, 2011). Peterson et al. (2013) report from scientific working groups attempting to synthesize the state of knowledge regarding the United States and variability in the weather gave particular attention to extremes of heat and cold waves, flooding, and droughts. Data over the last century shows patterns of increasing heat waves, with the 1930s and 1960s standing out as periods with the highest and lowest numbers. Cold waves were declining, with the 1980s and 2000s rating highest and lowest in the range. Causes linked to extreme temperatures are understood better than droughts. The IPCC points to the Deser et al. (2016) study of over five decades of winter air temperature trends across North America. Marion et al. (2021) examines concerns about climate change, finding that individual perception of global warming was linked to temperature change, but only with increased experience of hot dry days.

There is also growing recognition that communities of color and low-income communities intersect with environmental challenges, including the challenge of climate change, in unique ways. Experiences, perception, and impact must be considered in the context of spatial and geographic disparities and past history of environmental injustice, or the unfair treatment of people due to race, color, national origin, or income, concerning the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies (US EPA, 2014). One potential way to alleviate the impacts of climate change and environmental injustice is to ensure climate change policies are in place to protect those most impacted by climate change (i.e., people of color and individuals living below the poverty line). This study aims to describe the disparities in the degree and type of climate policies in place in the United States and to determine if there is a relationship between climate policies, experiences with climate change, and geographic distributions of people of color (POC) and individuals living below the poverty line.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1 Policy and Environmental Justice

Since its inception, the environmental justice movement in the United States has focused national attention on the issues related to ecological inequities impacting people of color and the poor. The initial spark for the movement came from a demonstration in Warren County, North Carolina in the early 1980s by the National Association for the Advancement of Colored People with hundreds protesting the dumping of hazardous waste in the predominantly African American community (Perez et al., 2015, US DOE, n.d.). Studies by the US GAO and United Church of Christ and the subsequent mobilization of stakeholders through conferences and summits in the following decade heightened national attention to the issues (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). Theoretical foundations of the movement are built on Rawls's (2004) definition of justice as fairness in distributing burdens and benefits. Bullard (1996) reinforced foundational principles of environmental justice, arguing that "all people and communities are entitled to equal protection of environmental and public health laws and regulations (p.493)." As a result of the increasing public awareness, government policy echoed these principles with a working group first established by US Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) in 1990, Executive Order 12898 on Environmental Justice four years later calling for federal agency strategies on environmental justice, followed by a subsequent plan to integrate environmental justice into activities of EPA by 2014 (Cutter, 1995; USEPA, 1994). The formal definition of environmental justice is "the fair

treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin, or income, with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies" (US EPA, 2022; Perez et al., 2015). By 2021 the Biden Administration through Executive Order 14008 established an advisory council on environmental justice to improve attention to the issues (White House, 2021). Goals were established through the Justice40 initiative to have 40% of federal investments, including those for clean energy and climate change, allocated to marginalized communities disproportionately impacted by environmental pollutants (White House, 2022). The White House also announced a range of other measures including strengthening the Environmental Justice Interagency Council with additional members including nine Secretaries, established a new office of Climate Change and Health Equity, set up Environmental Justice Officers within federal agencies and an Interagency Working Group to Decrease Risk of Climate Change to Children, the Elderly, People with Disabilities, and the Vulnerable (White House, Jan 27, 2021).

As global attention to the challenges of climate change increased in recent years, so has an interest in intersections between climate change and the mission to address environmental justice. Research highlights the challenges and vulnerabilities of people of color and the poor to climate change disruptions, including hurricanes, extreme weather, and difficulties in post-disaster recovery. Hurricane Katrina is a critical turning point in bringing attention to the environmental justice movement regarding climate issues (Perez et al., 2015). Bullard and Wright (2012) point out disparities in the impact of Hurricane Katrina on communities of color, including disaster response and preparation (Shepard & KC, 2015). Patnick et al. (2020) point to disparities in insurance access and spatial inequities in the proximity of communities of color to facilities emitting greenhouse gasses and pollutants linked to climate change from oil refineries, natural gas plants, and areas with high traffic levels. Researchers and activists focus on specific communities of interest such as 'Cancer Alley', in Louisiana where miles of polluting industries lie in communities with large minority populations, leading to elevated ranking by EPA for problematic discharges (Blodgett, 2006).

Spatial, racial, and ethnic disparities in the United States intertwine with higher mortality and morbidity in particular population groups, including the elderly (Maier et al., 2014). Lam et al. (2014) characterizes influences of social character, sensitivities, and place. Morello-Frosch (2009) highlighted disparities in wealth et al. and referred to inequities in risk from climate change as the "Climate Gap." Shepard and KC (2015) found communities with increased numbers of African Americans, with particular attention to coastal communities in the South Atlantic and Gulf, facing combined effects of hurricanes, heat waves, tornadoes, and droughts. Climate change impacts health, including elevated respiratory disease due to pollen, elevated air pollutants including sulfur and nitrogen dioxide and diesel, mental health, kidney disease, and obesity. Berberan et al. (2022) examined five years of evidence on climate and racial disparities that document death from heat, cardiovascular system, respiratory problems, and challenges to mental health. Other researchers note differential health impacts on low-income and people of color (Berry et al., 2010; Basu and Ostro, 2008; Akerlof, 2015; Levy and Paltz, 2015; Hanson et al., 2015; Bi et al., 2013). Berberan et al. (2022) reviewed studies related to a range of minority population groups in the United States, including not only Blacks but also Hispanics, Native Americans, Pacific Islanders, Asians, and multiracial populations, finding overwhelming consensus that increased temperature results in elevated death and sickness for adults of color in contrast to Whites.

Regional differences need to be considered as a relevant factor. Williams et al. (2020) point to regional differences in warmth and drought in the Southwest and western regions of the United States in this century compared to the last. Bullard et al. (2016) points to areas with dual challenges of extractive resources and high poverty levels, pointing out climate change disparities in the southern Atlantic coast. Shepard and KC's (2015) study of African Americans and climate change points to special vulnerability of this population not only because of high concentrations in the South Atlantic and Gulf coast regions with high levels of climate impact, but also urban concentrations. Beberan et al. (2022) also note differences in the regional distribution of research, with many studies focusing on racial disparities and climate in coastal areas. Studies on wildfires

were primarily from Western regions, those focused on hurricanes using data from the Atlantic coast and Southeast.

2.2 Subnational Climate Policy and Environmental Justice

Subnational action on climate policy has a variety of complex reasons for enactment, with an array of political and legal challenges to overcome. Some also suggest limitations of impact of policy at this level in comparison to federal level policies wider in scope (Wiener, 2007). Motivations for adoption and leadership on climate policy at the state level may include not only self-interest including economic or political benefit, federal stimulation of regulatory experimentation, policy entrepreneurs and a variety of domestic and international influences including responding to residents within a state (Fankhauser, 2016; Carlson, 2012; Rabe, 2004) Trachtman's (2020) analysis of the role of partisanship in state mitigation climate policy adoption concludes complex factors play a role. Political leanings of the state electorate play a greater role in adoption of certain policies such as renewable portfolio standards and distributed generation (which refers to energy such as renewables or rooftop solar generated away from centralized power plants), but not energy efficiency (USDOE, n.d.). However Democratic control of government at the state level was still more influential than divided government in the movement of energy efficiency policy. Matisoff (2008) highlights differences between internal political and economic dynamics versus factors related to influences of states within regions on each other related adoption of climate policy. The study affirms state characteristics as a more important driver than regional diffusion. State characteristics linked to increased likelihood of climate policy adoption include factors such as higher degree of population liberalism, industries emitting lower levels of carbon dioxide, a landscape with possibility for renewables but also greater per person emission of various air pollutants.

Disparate policies at state levels responding to projected challenges across the United States may be partial responses to increased understanding of impacts from climate change projected for infrastructure, property, social systems, and ecosystems (USGCRP, 2018). Ballew's (2021) survey evidence from over a ten-year period found people of color had higher levels of acknowledgement and acceptance of climate change and recognition of climate related risk than whites, although worry was greater among Latino's versus blacks while acceptance of harm to the country slightly greater among black. The study uncovered interesting differences related to intersection of party affiliation, race, ethnicity, and support for specific climate policies, with 91% of liberal whites supporting regulating power plants versus 84% of liberal Latinos and 75% liberal blacks. At the same time much higher levels of conservative blacks (64%) and Latinos (59%) showed support than conservative whites (43%). In terms of regulation of carbon dioxide, 91% Liberal whites, 83% of Liberal Hispanics, and 79% of liberal blacks were in support. Once again however, in terms of conservatives support among blacks was highest at 71% versus 66% among Latinos and 55% of whites.

The positions of influential organizations regarding climate change and environmental justice are also factors to examine. Some recognize the need for special attention to ensuring climate policy mitigates challenges for marginalized groups and communities of color. Organizations, including the American College of Physicians, issued a series of policy recommendations related to climate in 2016. However, it was not until 2022 that they included more explicit statements calling for placement of justice and health equity and justice "at the core" of policy response, including ensuring appropriate investments targeted for communities and populations particularly vulnerable and disproportionately affected (Crowley et al., 2022). While communities of color were found to be of increased risk for climate change impacts, some research suggest they not only produce fewer problematic emissions such as carbon dioxide related to greenhouse gas, but also are stronger supporters of legislation and policy in response to climate change (Shepard, KC 2015). Safarty et. al (2014) survey of members of an association of African American physicians, documents strong support for policies to reduce risk, along with affirmation of climate impacts on patients of color due impacts including allergy, air pollution, storms, and floods.

At the same time, other research such as Resnick (2022) also out conflict between some impacts of policies to address climate change and central environmental justice goals. Many actions to move society off dependence on greenhouse gas sources, including fossil fuels, have particularly harsh impacts on people of color and the poor. Winegarden (2014) for example, found regressive impacts on people of color and low income due to electricity price increases from proposed EPA regulations on power plants particularly in states like Ohio still relying on coal.). A 2021 study of blacks and Latinos in five states nationwide suggests that while 64% indicated they had experienced impacts of climate change, climate policy was secondary for the Biden Administration. It further suggests opportunities for deeper engagement that ties climate solutions with community priorities such as job growth from clean energy (Green Latinos et al, 2021).

3. Methodology of Study

3.1.2 Data Collection

This study aimed to characterize and examine correlations between the geographic distribution of changes in annual temperature, the percentage of people of color (POC), the percentage of people living below the federal poverty level, and climate change policies in the United States. This analysis utilizes publicly available data to examine whether the type and degree of climate change policies in the United States in 2021 was correlated with the percentage of POC living in each state in 2021, the percentage of individuals living below the federal poverty line living in each state in 2021, or the relative change in temperature over the past ten years (2011-2021).

Since 1895, The National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI) has collected statewide data from the U.S. Climate Divisional Database for the United States, excluding Hawaii and the Federal District of Columbia (NOAA National Centers for Environmental information, Climate at a Glance: Statewide Time Series, published February 2023, retrieved on March 4, 2023 from <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/monitoring/climate-at-a-glance/statewide/time-series>). This database provides historical data for climate analyses including data on annual temperature, extreme temperature, and precipitation. For this analysis, the average annual temperatures for 2011 and 2021 were extracted from the NCEI database to estimate the relative change in temperature for each state (see Appendix).

The Center for Climate and Energy Solutions collects data from each of the states, excluding the Federal District of Columbia, on the presence or absence of federal climate policies (<https://www.c2es.org/content/state-climate-policy/>). The data collected summarizes the absence or presence of climate policies related to greenhouse gas emissions targets, state climate actions plans, carbon pricing, electricity sector policies, and low carbon and alternative fuel standards in the form of interactive geospatial maps. A detailed description of each policy area can be found in **Table 1**. For this analysis, policy data for 2021 was extracted from the website maps and assembled into a dataset using a binary classification system (0: absent in 2021, 1: present in 2021). Detailed climate policy information for each state can be found in the Appendix.

Table 1: Summary of climate policy definitions

<i>Climate Policy</i>	<i>Definition</i>
Greenhouse gas emissions targets	A state-level goal to reduce emissions by a specific amount by a predetermined date
Climate action plans	Generally, including greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction targets and detailed actions the state can take to help meet those goals.
Carbon pricing	A market-based mechanism that creates financial incentives to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.
Electricity sector policies	A wide range of state policies help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the power sector. One of the most common state

Low carbon and alternative fuel standards	<p>policies is a portfolio standard that requires electric utilities to deliver a certain amount of electricity from renewable or clean energy sources.</p> <p>These include emissions standards, zero-emission vehicle deployment—which include both battery electric vehicles and fuel cell electric vehicles, and rebates and incentives for zero-emission vehicles and infrastructure, such as charging stations and hydrogen fueling infrastructure. A low-carbon fuel standard (LCFS) is aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions by requiring a shift to lower-carbon transportation fuels, such as biofuels, without prescribing a particular fuel type</p>
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Lastly, population demographic values from the 2021 United States Census Bureau’s American Community Survey, were extracted to estimate the percentages of POC (defined as any person who is not considered “white”) and percentages of individuals below the poverty level living in each state (See Appendix). Census data was assembled and wrangled using the tidycensus package in R (insert version) and was guided based on (<https://walker-data.com/census-r/an-introduction-to-tidycensus.html>).

3.1.2 Statistical Analysis

Correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the relationship between climate policy adoption, relative temperature change, and minority populations. Logistic regression was utilized to evaluate the relationship between relative temperature change, minority populations, and the type of climate policies in place. All analyses were set at a significance level of $P < 0.05$, indicating a statistically significant difference. The appendix provides details by state for each variable.

4. Results

4.1.1 Variation in the type and degree of climate policies in place

Figure 1 details the number and type of climate policies in the United States in 2021. The number of climate policies in place in 2021 ranged from 0 (AL, GA, ID, MS, NE, TN, WY) to 5 (CA, PA, WA) with a median number of 3 climate policies in place (Figure 1A). The most common climate policies were the U.S. State Electricity Portfolio Standards, U.S. State Climate Action Plans, and the Greenhouse Gas Emissions Targets (**Figure 1B**). Less common policies in place in 2021 were Low Carbon and Alternative Fuel Standard and State Carbon Pricing Policies (**Figure 1B**).

Figure 1: Summary of the degree and type of climate change policies in the United States in 2021. A) Numbers on states denote the total number of climate change policies in place for each state in 2021. B) Barplot summarizing the total number of each type of climate change policy in place in 2021.

Next, we sought to determine if the type of policies in place varied by state (**Figure 2**). The 7 states that had Low Carbon and Alternative Standards in place in 2021 included MN, MO, PA, CA, OR, and WA. In 2021, all states except ID, WY, NE, KY, TN, AR, LA, MS, AL, GA, SC, and FL had U.S. Electricity Portfolio Standards in place. Only 20% of states had State Carbon Pricing Policies in place in 2021. These states included CA, MA, MD, ME, NH, NY, PA, VA, VT, and WA. Less than half of the United States had Greenhouse Gas Emissions Targets in place compared to the 66% of states that had U.S. State Climate Action Plans in place in 2021.

Figure 2: Summary of climate change policies in the United States, by type, 2021 where the absence of the policy is denoted by the dark blue color and the presence of the policy is denoted by a light blue color.

Figure 3: Summary of the relative temperature change (2011- 2021) in the United States

4.1.2 Relationship between previous lived experiences with climate change and the type and degree of climate change policies

To address our initial research question on the relationship between previous lived experiences with climate change and the type and degree of climate change policies in the United States, we estimated the percent relative temperature change (2011 - 2021). The percent relative temperature averaged 2.29% and ranged from -1.85% (AK) to 7.62% (ND) (**Figure 3**). There was no correlation between the percent relative temperature change and the number of climate change policies in place in the states in 2021 ($r = 0.12$). Additionally, there was no significant difference in the relative temperature change in states with or without any of the climate policies in place further suggesting that previous lived experiences with climate change may have little to no impact on the choice to enact climate policies in the United States.

4.1.3 The relationship between vulnerable populations and the degree and type of climate change policies

Next to investigate the relationship between vulnerable populations and the degree and type of climate policies in place in the United States in 2021, we assembled racial and income demographic data for each state (see Appendix). When evaluating the relationship between the racial and income demographics in 2021 and the total number of climate policies instituted, we observed no significant correlation between the variables (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Correlation between racial and income demographics and the number of climate policies in place in the United States, 2021

<i>Racial and Income Demographic</i>	<i>Pearson Correlation Value</i>
White	-0.12
Black or African American	-0.11

Alaska Native and American Indian	-0.18
Asian American	0.54
Hispanic or Latino	-0.08
Income Below Poverty Level	-0.37

However, we observe disparities when comparing the type of climate policies in place and the racial and income demographics. States with U.S. Electricity Sector Policies exhibited significant differences in the demographic composition of Black or African American populations ($p = 0.008$) and Asian American populations ($p = 0.02$) compared to states without such policies. Notably, states lacking Electricity Sector Policies demonstrated a markedly higher population of African Americans (17%) in contrast to states with these policies (9%). Conversely, states without Electricity Sector Policies exhibited a lower percentage of Asian Americans (2%) compared to states with these policies (4%).

Differences in Asian American populations were observed between states with and without Carbon Pricing Policies ($p = 0.00008$). States implementing Carbon Pricing Policies demonstrated a higher percentage of Asian Americans (6%) in comparison to states without such policies (3%). Moreover, states with Carbon Pricing Policies had a lower percentage of individuals living below the poverty level (10%) than states lacking these policies (13%) ($p = 0.001$). Similarly, significant disparities in Asian American populations were identified between states with and without Greenhouse Gas Emissions Targets ($p = 0.02$), Climate Action Plans ($p = 0.01$), and Low Carbon Policies ($p = 0.03$). States with these respective policies demonstrated consistently higher percentages of Asian American populations compared to states without them.

Figure 4: Average racial and income demographics for states with and without A) Electricity Portfolio B) Low Carbon C) Carbon Pricing D) Greenhouse Gas Emissions or E) State Climate Action Plans in the United States, 2021

5. Discussion and Implications

The findings from this study highlight significant disparities in climate policy implementation across the United States in 2021, as well as their potential relationships with demographic factors. Our analysis revealed a wide variation in the number of climate policies across states, with some states—such as California and Washington—adopting comprehensive measures, while others, including Alabama and Georgia, enacted none. This divergence underscores the complexity of climate policy adoption in relation to state-specific contexts. Notably, we found that while certain policies, such as U.S. State Electricity Portfolio Standards and Climate Action Plans, were more prevalent, other crucial strategies like State Carbon Pricing Policies remained limited, implemented by only 20% of states. Our exploration into the relationship between previous lived experiences with climate change and the adoption of these policies yielded no significant correlation, suggesting that historical climate impacts may not directly inform state policy decisions. Furthermore, demographic analyses revealed that states with certain climate policies had distinct racial and income profiles, indicating that the implementation of climate policies may be influenced by, or may reinforce, existing social inequalities. These findings raise critical

questions about the intersection of climate policy and demographic factors, prompting further investigation into how vulnerable populations are represented in climate governance.

The significant variation in climate policies across states, as highlighted in our findings, underscores the fragmented nature of climate action in the United States. In 2021, while states like California and Washington implemented a diverse range of policies, others lagged significantly, with some states having no climate policies at all. This disparity aligns with the findings of Bromley-Trujillo (2020), which documented similar inconsistencies in state-level climate policymaking. Furthermore, the predominance of U.S. State Electricity Portfolio Standards and Climate Action Plans reflects a strategic focus on renewable energy and systematic planning, yet the low adoption of State Carbon Pricing Policies indicates a gap in comprehensive economic measures needed for effective emissions reduction. This gap is critical, as Vasi et al. point out, given that subnational policies play a crucial role in addressing environmental challenges and injustices. The limited presence of Low Carbon and Alternative Fuel Standards in only a handful of states further highlights the need for broader, coordinated efforts. Our analysis supports the assertion that integrating subnational actions with national strategies is vital for achieving climate goals, as noted in recent literature, which suggests that a comprehensive approach could potentially reduce emissions by up to 49% by 2030. The observed variations may not only reflect political and economic differences among states but also highlight an urgent need for policies that prioritize environmental justice and equitable resource distribution.

Our findings reveal a disconnect between lived experiences with climate change and the adoption of climate policies across the United States. The lack of significant correlation between temperature changes and the number of climate policies suggests that personal experiences may have limited influence on policymakers' decisions. This aligns with Yagenah et al.'s assertion that public support is a critical driver for climate policy adoption, indicating that emotional and experiential factors may not effectively translate into political action. Moreover, research by Trachtman et al. highlights the dominance of political over economic factors, suggesting that state governments may prioritize political dynamics rather than direct climate impacts when formulating their approaches. This underscores the importance of enhancing public engagement and addressing political barriers as more effective strategies for promoting robust climate action. Ultimately, our findings call for a deeper examination of the socio-political context surrounding climate policy adoption, emphasizing the need for strategies that galvanize public support and facilitate political will to address climate change effectively.

The demographic analyses conducted in this study reveal that states implementing specific climate policies exhibit distinct racial and income profiles, suggesting that the formulation and enforcement of these policies may be influenced by, or could potentially reinforce, existing social inequalities. These results highlight critical questions regarding the intersection of climate policy and demographic factors, particularly concerning the representation of vulnerable populations in climate governance. As such, the findings underscore the necessity for inclusive policy frameworks that address the needs and voices of marginalized communities. In the broader context of environmental justice and climate change in the United States, this research calls for a reevaluation of climate initiatives to ensure they do not inadvertently perpetuate disparities, but rather actively contribute to equitable solutions that benefit all demographic groups. Future investigations should explore strategies to enhance the participation of underrepresented communities in climate decision-making processes, thereby fostering a more just and sustainable future.

Our study has several limitations that warrant consideration. First, we defined lived experience with climate change solely through relative temperature change, which may not fully capture individuals' perceptions of climate impacts. Extreme weather events, for example, can significantly influence how communities respond to climate change and should be included in future research to provide a more comprehensive view of lived experiences.

Additionally, we did not control for political party affiliation, a crucial factor in the polarization of climate change policy in the United States. Understanding the interactions between political identity and policy adoption is essential, as party dynamics may shape responses to climate challenges at both state and local levels. Furthermore, while our focus on vulnerable groups centered on race and income, other factors such as age and disability also contribute to vulnerability in the context of climate change. Future studies should expand data collection to encompass a broader range of demographic factors, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of how various populations experience and respond to climate change. Addressing these limitations will enhance our insights into the complex interplay of factors influencing climate policy adoption.

In summary, this study reveals significant disparities in climate policy implementation across the United States, highlighting the intricate relationship between these policies and demographic factors. Our findings indicate that states with comprehensive climate measures often reflect specific racial and income profiles, suggesting a potential reinforcement of existing social inequalities. The lack of significant correlation between lived experiences of climate change and policy adoption points to the complex political dynamics that shape climate governance, emphasizing the need for strategies that enhance public engagement and support. As the U.S. grapples with environmental justice issues, our research calls for a critical reevaluation of climate initiatives to ensure they foster equitable solutions for all communities. Addressing the identified limitations will be essential for future research aimed at uncovering the nuanced factors influencing climate policy adoption and ensuring the representation of vulnerable populations in climate decision-making processes.

References

- Arias, P.A., N. Bellouin, E. Coppola, R.G. Jones, G. Krinner, J. Marotzke, V. Naik, M.D. Palmer, G.-K. Plattner, J. Rogelj, M. Rojas, J. Sillmann, T. Storelvmo, P.W. Thorne, B. Trewin, K. Achuta Rao, B. Adhikary, R.P. Allan, K. Armour, G. Bala, R. Barimalala, S. Berger, J.G. Canadell, C. Cassou, A. Cherchi, W. Collins, W.D. Collins, S.L. Connors, S. Corti, F. Cruz, F.J. Dentener, C. Dereczynski, A. Di Luca, A. Diongue Niang, F.J. Doblas-Reyes, A. Dosio, H. Douville, F. Engelbrecht, V. Eyring, E. Fischer, P. Forster, B. Fox-Kemper, J.S. Fuglestedt, J.C. Fyfe, N.P. Gillett, L. Goldfarb, I. Gorodetskaya, J.M. Gutierrez, R. Hamdi, E. Hawkins, H.T. Hewitt, P. Hope, A.S. Islam, C. Jones, D.S. Kaufman, R.E. Kopp, Y. Kosaka, J. Kossin, S. Krakovska, J.-Y. Lee, J. Li, T. Mauritsen, T.K. Maycock, M. Meinshausen, S.-K. Min, P.M.S. Monteiro, T. Ngo-Duc, F. Otto, I. Pinto, A. Pirani, K. Raghavan, R. Ranasinghe, A.C. Ruane, L. Ruiz, J.-B. Sallée, B.H. Samset, S. Sathyendranath, S.I. Seneviratne, A.A. Sörensson, S. Szopa, I. Takayabu, A.-M. Tréguier, B. van den Hurk, R. Vautard, K. von Schuckmann, S. Zaehle, X. Zhang, and K. Zickfeld, (2021) Technical Summary. In *Climate change 2021: The physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 33–144. doi:10.1017/9781009157896.002.
- A., Bi, L., Saniotis, A., & Nitschke, M. (2013). Vulnerability to extreme heat and climate change: is ethnicity a factor?. *Global health action*, 6(1), 21364.

<https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/fact-sheet/facts-about-the-us-black-population/#:~:text=Texas%20is%20home%20to%20the,single%2Drace%20Black%20people%20each>

- Akerlof, K. L., Delamater, P. L., Boules, C. R., Upperman, C. R., & Mitchell, C. S. (2015). Vulnerable populations perceive their health as at risk from climate change. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 12(12), 15419-15433.
- Ballew, M. T., Pearson, A. R., Schuldt, J. P., Kotcher, J. E., Maibach, E. W., Rosenthal, S. A., & Leiserowitz, A. (2021). Is the political divide on climate change narrower for people of color? Evidence from a decade of US polling. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 77, 101680.
- Barreca, A., Clay, K., Deschenes, O., Greenstone, M., & Shapiro, J. S. (2016). Adapting to climate change: The remarkable decline in the US temperature-mortality relationship over the twentieth century. *Journal of Political Economy*, 124(1), 105-159
- Basu, R., & Ostro, B. D. (2008). A multicounty analysis identifying the populations vulnerable to mortality associated with high ambient temperature in California. *American journal of epidemiology*, 168(6), 632-637.
- Berry, H. L., Bowen, K., & Kjellstrom, T. (2010). Climate change and mental health: a causal pathways framework. *International journal of public health*, 55, 123-132.
- Berberian A.G., Gonzalez DJX, Cushing LJ. (2022) Racial disparities in climate change-related health effects in the United States. *Current Environ Health Reports*. 9(3):451-464. doi: 10.1007/s40572-022-00360-w. Epub 2022 May 28. PMID: 35633370; PMCID: PMC9363288.
- Berberian, A. G., Gonzalez, D. J., & Cushing, L. J. (2022). Racial Disparities in Climate Change-Related Health Effects in the United States. *Current Environmental Health Reports*, 1-14.
- Blodgett, A. D. (2006). An analysis of pollution and community advocacy in 'Cancer Alley': Setting an example for the environmental justice movement in St James Parish, Louisiana. *Local Environment*, 11(6), 647-661.
- Bohle, H. G., Downing, T. E., & Watts, M. J. (1994). Climate change and social vulnerability: toward a sociology and geography of food insecurity. *Global environmental change*, 4(1), 37-48. (NOtES—not straight EJ article but seemed interesting to examine)
- Bullard, R. D., Gardezi, M., Chennault, C., & Dankbar, H. (2016). Climate change and environmental justice: A conversation with Dr. Robert Bullard. *Journal of Critical Thought and Praxis*, 5(2).
- Bullard, R. D. (1996). Environmental justice: It's more than waste facility siting. *Social science quarterly*, 77(3), 493-499.
- Burke, M., González, F., Baylis, P., Heft-Neal, S., Baysan, C., Basu, S., & Hsiang, S. (2018). Higher temperatures increase suicide rates in the United States and Mexico. *Nature climate change*, 8(8), 723-729.
- Carlson, A. E. (2012). Regulatory capacity and state environmental leadership: California's climate policy. *Fordham Envtl. L. Rev.*, 24, 63
- Center for Climate and Energy Solutions. (n.d.) State Climate Policy Maps <https://www.c2es.org/content/state-climate-policy/>

- Center for Climate and Energy Solutions (2022). U.S. State Climate Action Plans. <https://www.c2es.org/document/climate-action-plans/>
- Congressional Black Caucus. African Americans and Climate Change: An Unequal Burden
- Coumou, D., & Robinson, A. (2013). Historic and future increase in the global land area affected by monthly heat extremes. *Environmental Research Letters*, 8(3), 034018.heat extremes
- Coventry, P., & Okereke, C. (2017). Climate change and environmental justice. In *The Routledge handbook of environmental justice* (pp. 362-373). Routledge.
- Crowley R, Mathew S, Hilden D; Health and Public Policy Committee of the American College of Physicians(2022, Nov) Environmental health: A position paper from the American College of Physicians. *Ann Intern Med.* 175(11):1591-1593. doi: 10.7326/M22-1864. Epub 2022 Oct 25. PMID: 36279541
- Cutter, S. L. (1995). Race, class and environmental justice. *Progress in human geography*, 19(1), 111-122.
- Crowley R, Mathew S, Hilden D; Health and Public Policy Committee of the American College of Physicians*; Health and Public Policy Committee of the American College of Physicians. Environmental Health: A Position Paper From the American College of Physicians. *Ann Intern Med.* 2022 Nov;175(11):1591-1593. doi: 10.7326/M22-1864. Epub 2022 Oct 25. PMID: 36279541.
- Deser, C., L. Terray, and A.S. Phillips, (2016) Forced and internal components of winter air temperature trends over North America during the past 50 Years: Mechanisms and implications. *Journal of Climate*, 29(6), 2237–2258, doi: 10.1175/jcli-d-15-0304.1.
- Environmental Justice Paul Mohai,¹ David Pellow,² and J. Timmons Roberts³ *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 2009. 34:405–30 (see SECTION CLIMATE CHANGE)
- Fankhauser, S., Gennaioli, C., & Collins, M. (2016). Do international factors influence the passage of climate change legislation?. *Climate Policy*, 16(3), 318-331.
- Environmental Protection Agency (Aug 5, 2022) Sources of greenhouse gas emissions. <https://www.epa.gov/ghgemissions/sources-greenhouse-gas-emissions>
- Frosch, R. M., Pastor, M., Sadd, J., & Shonkoff, S. (2018). The climate gap: Inequalities in how climate change hurts Americans and how to close the gap. In *Planning for Climate Change* (pp. 138-150). Routledge.
- GreenLatinos, Third Way, & WE ACT for Environmental Justice (2021) Poll of Black and Latino?x Communities on Climate Change and the Clean Energy Transition. <https://www.weact.org/publications/poll-of-black-and-latino-x-communities-on-climate-change-and-the-clean-energy-transition>
- Hansen, A., Bi, L., Saniotis, A., & Nitschke, M. (2013). Vulnerability to extreme heat and climate change: is Williams, A. P., Cook, E. R., Smerdon, J. E., Cook, B. I., Abatzoglou, J. T., Bolles, K., ... & Livneh, B. (2020). Large contribution from anthropogenic warming to an emerging

- North American megadrought. *Science*, 368(6488), 314-318. ethnicity a factor?. *Global health action*, 6(1), 21364
- Hansen, A., Bi, L., Saniotis, A., & Nitschke, M. (2013). Vulnerability to extreme heat and climate change: is ethnicity a factor?. *Global health action*, 6(1), 21364.
- Krajick J. (2021, Sept 23) Why the US northeast coast is a global warming hot spot. *Columbia Climate School News*.
<https://news.climate.columbia.edu/2021/09/23/the-u-s-northeast-coast-is-a-global-warming-hot-spot-says-study/>
- Khatana, S. A. M., Werner, R. M., & Groeneveld, P. W. (2022). Association of extreme heat and cardiovascular mortality in the United States: A county-level longitudinal analysis from 2008 to 2017. *Circulation*, 146(3), 249-261.
- Levy, B. S., & Patz, J. A. (2015). Climate change, human rights, and social justice. *Annals of global health*, 81(3), 310-322.
- Marlon, J. R., Wang, X., Mildenerger, M., Bergquist, P., Swain, S., Hayhoe, K., ... & Leiserowitz, A. (2021). Hot dry days increase perceived experience with global warming. *Global Environmental Change*, 68, 102247.
- Marx, W., Haunschild, R., & Bornmann, L. (2021). Heat waves: a hot topic in climate change research. *Theoretical and applied climatology*, 146(1-2), 781-800.
- Matisoff, D. C. (2008). The adoption of state climate change policies and renewable portfolio standards: Regional diffusion or internal determinants? *Review of Policy Research*, 25(6), 527-546.
- Miller Hesed, C. D., & Ostergren, D. M. (2017). Promoting climate justice in high-income countries: lessons from African American communities on the Chesapeake Bay. *Climatic Change*, 143(1), 185-200.
- Miller Hesed, C. D., & Paolisso, M. (2015). Cultural knowledge and local vulnerability in African American communities. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(7), 683-687.
- Miranda, M. L., Hastings, D. A., Aldy, J. E., & Schlesinger, W. H. (2011). The environmental justice dimensions of climate change. *Environmental justice*, 4(1), 17-25
- Mohai P., Pellow D., Timmons J., Roberts T. (2009) *Environmental Justice Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 34:405–30
- Morello-Frosch, R., Pastor, M., Sadd, J. and Shonkoff, S. (2009). The climate gap: inequalities in how climate change hurts Americans and how to close the gap. USC Program for Environmental and Regional Equity, Los Angeles. Available at
http://www.barrfoundation.org/files/The_Climate_Gap.pdf (accessed on 1 April 2015).

NOAA National Centers for Environmental information. (2022) Climate at a Glance: Statewide Time Series, <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/monitoring/climate-at-a-glance/statewide/time-series>

Patnaik A., Son J., Feng A. , Ade C. (2020) Racial disparities and climate change. Princeton. <https://psci.princeton.edu/tips/2020/8/15/racial-disparities-and-climate-change>

Perez, A. C., Grafton, B., Mohai, P., Hardin, R., Hintzen, K., & Orvis, S. (2015). Evolution of the environmental justice movement: activism, formalization and differentiation. *Environmental Research Letters*, 10(10), 105002.

Phillips A., Dennis B, Samenow J., Muyskens J., Ahmed N. (2022 July 2) Summer in the United States is becoming hotter, longer and more dangerous. *Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/climate-environment/2022/07/02/summer-2022-climate-change-heat/>

Peterson, T. C., Heim Jr, R. R., Hirsch, R., Kaiser, D. P., Brooks, H., Diffenbaugh, N. S., ... & Wuebbles, D

(2013). Monitoring and understanding changes in heat waves, cold waves, floods, and droughts in the United States: state of knowledge. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 94(6), 821-834. Show this source to Jessica re analysis of temperature climate

Rawls, J. (2004). A theory of justice. In *Ethics* (pp. 229-234). Routledge.

Regions of the United States <https://studying-in-us.org/regions-of-the-united-states/>

Resnik, D. B. (2022). Environmental justice and climate change policies. *Bioethics*, 36(7), 735-741.

Sarfaty, M., Mitchell, M., Bloodhart, B., & Maibach, E. W. (2014). A survey of African American physicians on the health effects of climate change. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 11(12), 12473-12485

Schlosberg, D., & Collins, L. B. (2014). From environmental to climate justice: climate change and the discourse of environmental justice. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 5(3), 359-374. doi: 10.1002/wcc.275

Sharp, E. B., Daley, D. M., & Lynch, M. S. (2011). Understanding local adoption and implementation of climate change mitigation policy. *Urban Affairs Review*, 47(3), 433-457.

Shepherd, M., & KC, B. (2015). Climate change and African Americans in the USA. *Geography Compass*, 9(11), 579-591.

Shwom, R., Bidwell, D., Dan, A., & Dietz, T. (2010). Understanding US public support for domestic climate change initiatives: what is

- motivating state and local governments to address a global problem and what does this say about federalism and environmental law. *Urb. Law.*, 38, 1015. *change policies. Global Environmental Change*, 20(3), 472-482.
- Stern, D. I., & Kaufmann, R. K. (2014). Anthropogenic and natural causes of climate change. *Climatic change*, 122, 257-269.
- Turrentine J. (2022, September 13) What are the causes of climate change. Natural Resources Defense Council. <https://www.nrdc.org/stories/what-are-causes-climate-change>
- Trachtman, S. (2020). What drives climate policy adoption in the US states?. *Energy Policy*, 138, 111214.
- US DOE (n.d.) Environmental justice history. Office of Legacy Management. [Energy.gov https://www.energy.gov/lm/services/environmental-justice/environmental-justice-history](https://www.energy.gov/lm/services/environmental-justice/environmental-justice-history)
- US Department of Energy. (n.d.) Renewable Energy: Distributed Generation Policies and Programs: Office of State and Community Energy Programs. <https://www.energy.gov/scep/slsc/renewable-energy-distributed-generation-policies-and-programs#:~:text=Distributed%20generation%20is%20the%20term,generation%20sources%20from%20power%20plants>.
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (1994 Feb 16) Summary of Executive Order 12898 - Federal actions to address environmental justice in minority populations and low-income populations. <https://www.epa.gov/laws-regulations/summary-executive-order-12898-federal-actions-address-environmental-justice>
- US EPA. (2022, Dec 6) Learn about environmental justice. <https://www.epa.gov/environmentaljustice/learn-about-environmental-justice>
- US Global Change Research Program. (2018) Fourth National Climate Assessment Impacts, Risks, and Adaptation in the United States: Fourth National Climate Assessment, Volume II [Reidmiller, D.R., C.W. Avery, D.R. Easterling, K.E. Kunkel, K.L.M. Lewis, T.K. Maycock, and B.C. Stewart (eds.)]. U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC, USA, 1515 pp. doi: 10.7930/NCA4.2018. <https://nca2018.globalchange.gov/>
- USGCRP (2018) Impacts, risks, and adaptation in the United States: Fourth national climate assessment, Volume II: [Reidmiller, D.R., C.W. Avery, D.R. Easterling, K.E. Kunkel, K.L.M. Lewis, T.K. Maycock, and B.C. Stewart (eds.)]. U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC, USA, 1515 pp. doi: 10.7930/NCA4.2018.
- Vose, R.S., D.R. Easterling, K.E. Kunkel, A.N. LeGrande, and M.F. Wehner, (2017): Temperature changes in the United States. In: *Climate Science Special Report: Fourth National Climate Assessment, Volume I* [Wuebbles, D.J., D.W. Fahey, K.A. Hibbard, D.J. Dokken, B.C. Stewart, and T.K. Maycock (eds.)]. U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC, USA, pp. 185-206, doi: 10.7930/JON29V45

White House (2021, January 27) Executive order on tackling the climate crises at home and abroad.

<https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/presidential-actions/2021/01/27/executive-order-on-tackling-the-climate-crisis-at-home-and-abroad/>

White House. (2021.) White House Environmental Justice Advisory Council.
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/environmentaljustice/white-house-environmental-justice-advisory-council/>

White House (2022) Justice 40: A whole of government initiative.
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/environmentaljustice/justice40/>

/

Wiener, J. B. (2007). Think globally, act globally: The limits of local climate policies. *University of Pennsylvania Law Review*, 155(6), 1961-1979.

Wilson, S. M., Richard, R., Joseph, L., & Williams, E. (2010). Climate change, environmental justice, and vulnerability: an exploratory spatial analysis. *Environmental Justice*, 3(1), 13-19.

Wilson, S. M., Richard, R., Joseph, L., & Williams, E. (2010). Climate change, environmental justice, and Williams, A. P., Cook, E. R., Smerdon, J. E., Cook, B. I., Abatzoglou, J. T., Bolles, K., ... & Livneh, B. (2020). Large contribution from anthropogenic warming to an emerging North American megadrought. *Science*, 368(6488), 314-318. vulnerability: an exploratory spatial analysis. *Environmental Justice*, 3(1), 13-19.

Winegarden W. (2014) The regressive impact on Ohio's Lower Income and African American Families from EPA's proposed regulation on carbon dioxide emissions. PRI.
https://www.pacificresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/EPA_Ohio_rFweb.pdf

Yeganeh, A. J., McCoy, A. P., & Schenk, T. (2020). Determinants of climate change policy adoption: A meta-analysis. *Urban Climate*, 31, 100547.

Zhou, Y., & Shepherd, J. M. (2010). Atlanta's urban heat island under extreme heat conditions and potential mitigation strategies. *Natural Hazards*, 52, 639-668.